

The Impact of Work Engagement on the Agility of the Organization's Workforce X

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ABSTRACT: Digital transformation is increasingly necessary in the public sector and is a government strategy imperative. ASNs working in Organization X need to be agile to adapt to the changing environment and the current digital acceleration. Higher work engagement among employees will lead to increased motivation and improved workforce agility. This research takes a quantitative approach in the form of non-experimental methods. Regression analysis was used as the analysis technique to investigate the impact of work engagement on employee agility of ASN employees in company X. The study sampling consisted of 122 interviewees. The results indicate a significant positive correlation between work engagement and workforce agility. Further research is expected to deepen the information by interviewing relevant parties to verify and strengthen the phenomenon.

KEYWORDS: Digital Transformation, Workforce Agility, Work Engagement, ASN

I. INTRODUCTION

A paradigm shift in the global economy and society has been triggered by the rapid progress of digital transformation. The use of digitalization to achieve economic and business goals is a positive outcome of digital transformation. Furthermore, governments are adopting digital transformation to improve the quality of public services provided to citizens (WATIKNAS, 2022). Digital transformation has transitioned from being a technological opportunity to becoming a necessity for managing growing needs (Kraus et al., 2021). This shift has brought about significant changes in many organizations, introducing new processes and mechanisms that can impact business operations.

Hess, Benlian, Matt, and Wiesbock (2016) claim that companies that do not quickly develop and implement digital transformation strategies will not be able to compete in the new digital reality era. Digital transformation is a crucial strategy that governments in the public sector must implement, as disruptive digital technologies are changing every aspect of society and life. Through digital transformation, organizations aim to re-engineer their business processes, create new ways of working, and interact with an increasingly informed public that demands efficiency and transparency. However, digital transformation in the public sector is still in its infancy. There is little evidence of how governments and public sector organizations are approaching it. Digital transformation can bring significant benefits to governments and citizens by improving efficiency and service quality in the public service sector. The pace of digital transformation is rapidly increasing, particularly in response to new digital expectations from customers and employees. Therefore, public service organizations are now using technology to enhance employee experience and ultimately improve their business performance.

Digital talent development is a critical aspect of digital transformation. The most effective digital talent programs extend beyond recruitment. They should encompass an employee value proposition that attracts and retains top talent, agile and digital HR processes to locate, manage, and train talent, and a supportive environment where top talent can flourish (McKinsey & Company, 2020). Organization X implements policies around the four pillars of the digital literacy program: digital skills, digital security, digital culture, and digital ethics for the development of digital talent. According to the Head of the Personnel and Organisation Bureau of the Secretariat General of the Ministry of Communication and Information, the four pillars of digital literacy are currently encouraging ASNs to adopt a more open-minded, open-hearted, and open-willed approach to become problem solvers in their respective work units. This shift in mindset aims to transform the current reactive work culture into a proactive one, which was previously slow to agile (KOMINFO, 2022). State Civil Apparatus (ASN) working in public service organizations are now required to be proactive rather than reactive. This means they must be agile and able to adapt to environmental changes, keeping up with the current digital acceleration.

Agile employees are well-trained, flexible, and can adapt quickly to offer solutions to new challenges. According to a survey conducted by Aon, 85% of leaders and HR professionals in the Asia Pacific region believe that workforce agility is key to future success. Organizations need to prioritize workforce agility to succeed in the future. To achieve this, organizations need to develop

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strategies that focus on increasing work innovation and proactive initiatives. Workforce agility has become a defining characteristic of sustainable and competitive organizations (Munteanu et al., 2020). Workforce agility is recognized as a management strategy that enables companies to respond quickly and effectively to threats and opportunities in a competitive and volatile business environment (Tessarini & Saltorato, 2021). Tien, Hsu, and Hsing (2020) demonstrate that the enhancement of workforce agility can motivate employees to expand their knowledge and skills, both within and beyond their current job responsibilities. This, in turn, makes it easier to collaborate and promotes innovative thinking.

Work engagement has received significant attention in the field of organizational management literature. It is considered an influential factor in adaptive performance. Individuals who are highly engaged at work tend to focus more energy on their tasks and are better equipped to handle the dynamics of change (Park et al., 2020). Work engagement is defined as employees' psychological connection with their job tasks, where they feel emotionally and cognitively involved (Khusanova, Kang, & Choi, 2021). However, in reality, only a small percentage of employees worldwide are engaged in their work. According to Gallup's 2017 report titled 'State of the Global Workplace', only 15% of employees worldwide are engaged or highly engaged in their work and workplace, while the remaining 67% are not engaged or psychologically disconnected from their work and business.

Work engagement is an important asset for organizations as it fosters employee loyalty and facilitates agile working (Aidan, Alibabaei, & Mohammadi, 2018). High levels of engagement in workers are associated with an increased generation of innovative and creative ideas due to their openness to new experiences (Orth and Volmer, 2017). When employees are highly engaged with the organization and its components, their performance tends to improve (Nurbaity & H. Sulisty, 2013). This can provide a competitive advantage for the company through increased productivity (Supriyanto, Ekowati, & Pujianto, 2021). According to Pratamasari's research (2019), employees who exhibit higher levels of work engagement are more motivated to perform their tasks to the best of their ability, thereby increasing labor agility. This study aims to investigate the impact of work engagement on workforce agility in ASNs employed by Organisation X.

II. METHOD

This research uses a quantitative, non-experimental approach. The analysis technique used is multiple linear regression analysis because this research wants to know the influence between two variables, namely work engagement on workforce agility which is carried out on ASN employees in organization X. The sample in this study consisted of 122 respondents. Data collection was carried out from July 3 2022 to July 20 2022 by distributing an online questionnaire in the form of a gform link via WhatsApp broadcast message. The measuring tool for this research uses the workforce agility scale (Sherehiy, 2008) which consists of 39 questions, and UWES-17 (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004) which consists of 3 aspects with a total of 17 questions. Before collecting data, the researcher carried out a trial by measuring instruments. After analysis, there were 4 invalid items on the workforce agility scale measuring tool.

III. RESULT

This research aims to determine the effect of work engagement on workforce agility in ASNs who work in public sector service organizations, namely Organizations.

Table 1. Test Results of the Coefficient of Determination of Work Engagement on Workforce Agility

R	R²	Sig.
0.597	0.357	0.000

To test the research model, the Linear Regression technique was used with SPSS 23 software. Based on the table above, it can be seen that the coefficient of determination R² is 0.357. This result can be interpreted as meaning that 35.7% of the work engagement variable influences workforce agility. However, the remaining 64.3% was influenced by other variables not explained in the research.

IV. DISCUSSION

Digital transformation in the public service sector has significant implications, including improved efficiency, transparency, participation, and service quality. Organizations that provide their workers with the best digital tools, capabilities, and environment will be in a better position to retain key talent, attract new talent, and see benefits in areas such as productivity, creativity, and customer satisfaction. Therefore, the government should prioritize the development of digitally skilled civil servants to ensure successful digital transformation and sustainable competitiveness. Employees must acquire the necessary competencies to innovate according to performance demands, adapt to new conditions using company capabilities, and respond to changes. This study aims to investigate the impact of work engagement on labor agility. The findings indicate that work engagement has a significant impact of 35.7% on labor agility. Organizations highly value agile employees due to their ability to

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effectively implement new and innovative work programs. This is because agile employees are flexible and adaptable when faced with new organizational policies.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The research findings indicate that work engagement and workforce agility are interconnected. Workforce agility is a valuable asset for organizations, especially during the accelerated digital transformation triggered by the COVID-19 pandemic. By boosting work engagement, employees are more likely to innovate and generate new ideas, thus becoming more agile. This research aims to provide valuable insights into the development of Industrial Psychology, particularly in enhancing workforce agility in ASN employees within an organization. To further strengthen the phenomenon being studied, it is hoped that future research will involve conducting interviews with relevant parties to gather more in-depth information.

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